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RESEARCH IN AFRICAN LANGUAGES AND LINGUISTICS

(RALL)

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RESEARCH IN AFRICAN LANGUAGES AND LINGUISTICS (RALL)
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EDITORIAL NOTE

The journal *Research in African Languages and Linguistics* (RALL) is the actualisation of the dream of a group of academic and non-academic staff of the Department of Linguistics and African (formerly, Nigerian) Languages here at the University of Ibadan to provide some channel, no matter how modest, devoid of the bureaucracy that has tended to bug-down departmental outfits through which they and their colleagues here and elsewhere in Nigeria (and other parts of Africa?) can get to be heard on a fairly regular basis. This dream has been edged on by one or two people outside academics who by their insistence finally drummed it home to us that no one outside academia can provide academics with the means to be heard, and that complaining about the absence of viable journals could never by itself solve any problem.

We would also like to add that we have been very much inspired and encouraged by the emergence without any fanfare of the *Review of English and Literary Studies* (RELS) currently edited by Professor Sam Asein of the Department of English here at Ibadan who has graciously made available to us the benefit of his experience with RELS.

This foundation issue of RALL is dedicated to Professor CARL HOFFMAN, foundation Head of the Department of Linguistics and Nigerian (now African) Languages who retired from the services of the University of Ibadan in 1978 and is currently occupying the first of the two chairs of African Studies at the University of Bayreuth in Western Germany.

The decision to dedicate this first issue of RALL to Professor Hoffmann has been predicated on two major considerations. The first centres around his widely recognised concern and commitment to the building up of a valuable body of useful knowledge about African Languages in general, and the smaller, lesser-known languages of Nigeria in particular and continuing research into them.

More than ten years after he suddenly decided to relinquish his post here at Ibadan for strong, family reasons, his commitment and his almost palpable concern for the welfare and general academic development of his former department, students and/or junior colleagues has not waned one bit. In his time, first at the University of Hamburg and subsequently the University of Bayreuth, he has exploited every available opportunity to get some of his former wards and colleagues to share the results of their continuing research with German colleagues who are generally much more familiar with the results of research into Linguistics and the Languages of East and Central Africa than with those of the West African sub-region. Therein lies the second of the two considerations mentioned earlier.

In all of Professor Hoffman's contacts with his former colleagues and/or students here at Ibadan, he has never stopped worrying about *how* more opportunities can be provided for them to not only hear what Europe and America have to say in their chosen field but also, if not more particularly, to get heard by their colleagues in Europe and America and retain the capacity to continue vigorous and practical research in the prevailing economic climate of a debt-ridden Africa suffocating under the stranglehold of the IMF and the World Bank.

The originators of RALL have therefore derived much inspiration, encouragement and moral and other support from his insistence on the necessity to at least TRY and get something going, no matter how modest, and simply count on commitment and vision to see them through, without allowing considerations tied to matching any particular kind of quality associated with firmly established Euro-American journals to discourage them.

One of the most striking results of all of the above is that to many of his colleagues in Germany, whether or not they are willing to admit to it openly, Professor Carl Hoffmann is an unrepentant African trapped in a white skin who today must bear the burden of living in an arrogant, Euro-centric world faced with an Africa that for fairly obvious reasons has difficulty inspiring the respect of any but the most humane, gracious, understanding and generous.

It is against this background that the need for this first issue of RALL to celebrate the value in

real terms of the opportunity that some of us have had to interact with and get to know and appreciate what the likes of Professor Carl Hoffman represent must be properly appreciated. No one with anything but the vaguest familiarity with Professor Hoffman's dreams, hopes and anxieties vis à vis linguistic research in this country can fail to join us in saluting the guts and commitment of this true friend of African scholarship.

The majority of the papers in this first issue of RALL have come from former students of Professor Hoffmann and students of these, or what some of us at Ibadan are wont to describe as Hoffmann's academic children and grand children, and others to whose careers Hoffman's presence at Ibadan in the 60's and 70's made tremendous contributions, one way or the other. As we salute the doggedness of Professor Hoffman's commitment to Africa, we can only hope that RALL's offering here and in subsequent issues will justify the faith he has had, and continues to have in some of us and our capacity, academic or otherwise, to survive in the face of the greatest odds.

As we go to Press at a time when the Department of Linguistics and African Languages here at Ibadan looks set to face the greatest test of its capacity to stay afloat in line with the vision of its founding fathers (and mothers too), we wish to thank all those who either helped create the dream represented by RALL, nurtured that dream over the last twenty or so months, or insisted on its actualisation in spite of myriads of problems.

Augusta Phil Omamor
for & on behalf of:
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THE LIMITS OF ACCURACY IN THE DESIGN OF ORTHOGRAPHIES

Ben O. Elugbe
(University of Ibadan)

0. Introduction¹

Current government interest in the use of minority languages of Nigeria in education directly challenges linguists to pay greater attention to reducing these minority languages to writing. Since most of these languages are unwritten or have inaccurate writing systems at variance with the facts of the languages, the linguist must of necessity attempt an accurate analysis of them as the basis for the writing systems he will propose. In trying to base his proposals on his accurate analyses, he will find himself face to face with the problem of changing established habits and matching theory against practice.

In this paper, I present an analysis of the sound system of the Agbarho dialect of Urhobo (regarded as the standard Urhobo dialect). In particular, I will examine the vowel system both in terms of analysis and in terms of orthographic practice. Urhobo is an Edoid language and is the best-known of the Southwestern Edoid subgroup.

1. The Vowels of Urhobo

Phonetically, there are seven oral and seven nasalized vowels in Urhobo, each oral vowel being matched with a nasalized one.

(1)	Oral	Nasalized
	i	ĩ
	u	ũ
	e	ẽ
	o	õ
	ɛ	ɛ̃
	o	õ
	a	ã

Oral and nasalized vowels contrast, as in the following examples:

- | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------|
| (2) a. òrɪ pomade | e. fɪ be quiet |
| èrɪ fish | fɪ̃ be neat, clean |
| b. sè call | f. ècɔ́ to steal |
| sè̃ deny, refuse | ètɔ́ hair |
| c. écɪ̃ door | g. sù rule, lead |
| úké egg | fù̃ extinguish |
| d. fà thresh (e.g. rice) | |
| fà̃ loosen, free | |

I have so far not found /ŋ/ after stops or fricatives. Even so the evidence for postulating significant nasalization and therefore recognizing a set of seven nasal vowels is quite comprehensive, especially as the cases of /ĩ/ and /õ/ are beyond doubt.

2. Vowel harmony

An examination of the noun normally suggests that there is no vowel harmony in Urhobo:

- | | |
|-----------------|----------------|
| (3) èvé 'goat' | èdá 'matchets' |
| ègò 'bottles' | òdè 'name' |
| òbò 'doctor' | òdà 'matchet' |
| òtá 'hand, arm' | asõ 'night' |
| | òsè 'suitor' |

However, vowel patterning in the verb throws up some evidence of vowel harmony. The 3rd person singular form of the simple past is presented below:

- | | | | | |
|--------|---|-----|----|---------------|
| (4) a. | ò | fí | ɛ̀ | 'he threw' |
| b. | ò | sé | rì | 'he called' |
| c. | ò | ɛ́ | fè | 'he ate' |
| d. | ò | dé | rè | 'he bought' |
| e. | ò | dá | fè | 'he drank' |
| f. | ò | rɛ́ | rè | 'he survived' |
| g. | ò | có | rì | 'he stole' |
| h. | ò | só | rò | 'he sang' |
| i. | ò | rú | rù | 'he did' |

Students of vowel harmony would immediately identify the oral alternation in the 3rd person singular pronoun. Based on that alternation, the vowels fall into two groups (we ignore nasalized vowels which behave exactly as their oral counterparts):

- | | | |
|-----|---------|---------|
| (5) | group 1 | group 2 |
| | i u | e o |
| | e o | ɛ ɔ |
| | | a |

Two vowels, /e/ and /o/, appear in both groups because they can go with either of the two shapes of the 3rd person singular pronoun (cf 4b with 4c and 4g with 4h). If we now label e and o in group 1 as /e₁ o₁/ and those in group 2 as /e₂ o₂/, (5) can be presented as (6):

- | | | |
|-----|-------------------------------|-------------------------------|
| (6) | group 1 | group 2 |
| | i u | e ₂ o ₂ |
| | e ₁ o ₁ | e o |
| | | a |

The obvious conclusion we should draw is that Urhobo's seven vowels are derived historically from nine. An absolute neutralization rule has merged /e₂ o₂/ with /e₁ o₁/. From our knowledge of vowel systems in the rest of Edoid, we know that the two vowels suggested by (e₂ o₂) are /I ɔ/ respectively. The closely related languages of Isoko and Erywa both have nine vowel systems which include /I/ and /ɔ/.

Further evidence in support of the analysis of /e₂ o₂/ as /I ɔ/ comes from the infinitive/genrund forms of these verbs:

- | | | |
|--------|---------------------------|------------------------|
| (7) a. | èfjó 'to throw, throwing' | (ff throw) |
| b. | èsé 'to call, calling' | (sé ₁ call) |
| c. | ègbé 'to eat, eating' | (éé ₂ eat) |

- d. èdè 'to buy, buying' (dè buy)
 e. èdá 'to drink, drinking' (dà drink)
 f. èró 'to survive, surviving' (rò survive)
 g. ècò 'to steal, stealing' (cò₁ steal)
 h. èswó 'to sing, singing' (sò₂ sing)
 i. èwó 'to do, doing' (wó do)

Matching (7) with (6), we note that i u e₂ o₂ are the four vowels which, as verb stem vowels, attract a suffixal o or ɔ and then become glide. /i u/ are the closest vowels in group 1 while /e₂ o₂/ are the closest in group 2. We may therefore justifiably set up e₂ and o₂ as I and ɔ respectively.

(8) The nine vowels of Urhobo

EXPANDED/ART		NONEXPANDED/NON-ATR	
i	u	I	ɔ
e	o	ɛ	ɔ

a

In 8 we have now entered I and ɔ even though what we have are e, o. We have also properly entered the vowels under the typical West African vowel harmony labels [EXPANDED]/[ATR]. Group 1 vowels are [+ATR] while group 2 are [-ATR].

This analysis receives further support from the vowel systems of Okpe and Uvwie (Uvwie) where Hoffman (1973) and Omamor (1973) have reported similar phenomena and analysis.

4. The representation of Urhobo vowels in Urhobo orthography

In sections 2 and 3 above, we discussed two aspects of Urhobo vowels: nasalization and vowel harmony. We noted that nasalization is significant and, in section 3, we demonstrated not only that there is vowel harmony in Urhobo but also that Urhobo operates a nine-vowel system even though it contains only seven vowels phonetically.

In Urhobo orthography, the representation of nasalization follows the more common practice of indicating nasalization by writing an n after the vowel or vowels to be nasalized. Thus the items in (2) above would be written orthographically as in (9):

- (9) a. òrí pomade² d. fà thresh (e.g. rice)
 èrìn fish fàn loosen, free
- b. se call e. fò be quiet
 sen deny, refuse fòn be clean, neat
- c. écè door f. ècò to steal
 úkèn egg ètòn hair
- g. sù rule, lead
 fùn extinguish

This practice is suspended in a number of cases. For example, although [n] and [ɲ] belong to the same phoneme /ɲ/ ([n] occurs always before nasal vowels while [ɲ] occurs only before oral vowels), Urhobo orthography does not use one symbol for the one significant sound represented by [ɲ] and [n]. Instead, both are written:

(10) [l] and [n] in Urhobo orthography

phonetic	phonemic	orthographic
[ni] 'look'	/lĩ/	ni
[nẽ] 'defecate'	/lẽ/	ne
[nũ] 'pull out'	/lũ/	nu
[lò] 'shine'	/lò/	lo
[là] 'burn'	/là/	la

It may be argued that this represents a case of over-differentiation: more symbols are used than absolutely necessary. It should be noted, however, that the availability of two Roman symbols, one for each allophone, has been helpful. In the same language /w/ and /j/ both have two allophones each — one oral and the other nasalized. In each case, the difference is indicated through the nasality of the vowel (as against the l/n case where the difference is indicated in the allophones):

(11) phonetic	orthographic
òwò 'leg'	owò
úwẽ 'nose'	úwén
jà 'write'	yà
ƶá 'walk'	yaní

The situation with the vowels is different. Urhobo orthography uses seven vowel symbols and represents exactly seven vowels.

12. phonetic	phonemic	orthographic (phonetic)	orthographic (phonemic)
i	i	i	i
e	e ₁	e	e
e	e ₂	e	i̇
ɛ	ɛ	ė	ė
a	a	a	a
ɔ	ɔ	ȯ	ȯ
o	o ₁	o	o
o	o ₂	o	u̇
u	u	u	u

Omamor (1988 and personal communication) prefers the orthographic representation founded on the 'accurate' analysis of the language as having nine vowels. In fact, in her 1988 work on Okpe, she introduces exactly the phonemically based set of symbols (see 1.2 again)³. The over-riding consideration in such a proposal is accuracy. In particular, the following kind of question is posed. Given two verbs, so sing' and co 'steal', for example, how is the learner or the reader to know which o (o₁ or

o_2) he is dealing with at any given moment? In order to save the learner or reader this problem, su and co are proposed: the o_2 in so 'sing' is a [-ATR] vowel and is therefore subdotted. The same argument applies to e_1 and e_2 : e_2 is a [-ATR] vowel: i . In this way the orthography properly represents the underlying phonemic vowel contrasts in the language.

However, there are compelling reasons why one should ignore the apparent accuracy of the nine-vowel approach to the writing of these vowels in favour of the seven-vowel approach. Some of the reasons relate to our interpretation of accuracy; others derive from practical attempts at teaching the accuracy-oriented system.

First of all, it is by no means obvious or certain that the difference between the two e's and o's is now lexically relevant even though it remains valid for certain phonotactic operations. For example, a native speaker invariably knows whether the e in a word should undergo glide formation or not. The learner can be taught to recognize these. A dictionary of Urhobo can mark such vowels where they occur.

Secondly, the phonemically 'accurate' system runs into problems with vowel cooccurrence. Given two vowels, one at the beginning and the other in the stem (e.g. oda 'matchet'), this system would have to look at the stem to decide that the o in oda is in fact u (representing O or o_2), and that the e in eda 'matchets' is i (representing I or e_2). In actual practice this system is not foolproof. Both in individual polysyllabic words and in compound or complex words, it is not always clear just which o's and e's must be treated as [-ATR] and so subdotted.

In practical situations both in and outside the classroom, the native speakers prove to be more at home with the seven-vowel approach than with the nine. This was obvious from our experiences with prospective teachers of Okpe when I and two other colleagues attempted to teach them a new, accurate nine-vowel orthography. We had to resort to such tricks as 'if the first vowel of the word is subdotted or is a, then change e to i and o to u . By this rule ebe book' would become ebi . Similarly, we had to say 'if the stem vowel (usually the vowel after the first consonant) is subdotted or is a, change e to i and o to u '. That we had to resort to such nonlinguistic techniques is, in my view, evidence that we were working against the linguistic instincts of the native speakers.⁴

I suspect that it may be argued that these teachers were labouring under interference from the seven-vowel Urhobo orthography. However, even that would only support our argument here which is that the seven-vowel Urhobo practice was well-assimilated. And the reason why this seven-vowel system would be so well assimilated would be because it is nearer the speakers' competence in, or inherent knowledge of, the vowel system of Urhobo.

In these circumstances, a seven-vowel analysis of Urhobo is valid for orthographic purposes. Where there is absolute neutralization such as the one caused by the historical change by which Proto-South-Western Edoid $*\text{E}$ e and $*\text{O}$ o without reference to context, then the designer of a writing system as a whole will do well to base his alphabet on the post-neutralization forms which are more phonetic.

Again, even the fact that e_2 and o_2 behave like I and O respectively in glide-forming environments does not reduce from the validity of our position: by becoming glides between a consonant and another (non-identical) vowel, the vowels already mark themselves out as close vowels. In any case, in such situations, we can write them as i and u respectively without any problem. In fact, any attempt to discriminate between i and e_2 and between u and o_2 in vowel sequences in stems is bound to fail. For example, Proto-Edoid $vi\epsilon$ 'cry, ween' and $bhi\text{O}$ both have $i\epsilon$ reflexes in Urhobo $vi\epsilon$ [$vj\epsilon$] and $vbie$ [$uj\epsilon$] respectively. There is no need trying to be accurate by writing $vi\epsilon$: the two sequences, one originally [-ATR] and the other [+ATR], have now become $i\epsilon$. The subdotted ϵ in the sequence does not help us to determine which i should be subdotted. The only way we can tell which of the sequences was originally [+ATR] and which [-ATR] is to try them in harmony inducing environments. Then we find $vi\epsilon$ attracts the prefix o while $vbie$ attracts o . Therefore, the $i\epsilon$ sequence in $vi\epsilon$ is [-ATR] while that in $vbie$ is [+ATR]!

Finally, any revision of an orthography must take into account just how established that system is. Although Urhobo has no comprehensive and modern writing system, the publication of the Bible in

Urhobo is a major achievement of the system now in practice. Any proposals for change will have to take into account the system adopted in the bible. To that extent, radical innovations such as those of Omamor (1988) are still easier to pursue in languages without any literature than in the languages with some established tradition.

Notes

1. This paper was first proposed for the LAN Conference in Port Harcourt two years ago. However, although the idea was born much earlier, the paper has gained from my experiences with teachers of Okpe late last year.
2. There is no tone-marking in current Urhobo orthography.
3. It should be noted that, phonetically, Urhobo is more clearly identified as a seven-vowel system than Okpe or Uvbie.
4. I have also found with Adult Education students in my practical orthography class that the seven vowel system is easier to learn for native speakers of Urhobo and Uvbie.

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